

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' INTEREST IN PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, views on the process of formation of a person as a specialist are presented in students' desire and interest in the profession, their formation and development in cooperation with parents.

Expected results can be achieved if students are motivated and interested in professions, their formation and development are carried out in cooperation with parents. The author's views on the process of formation of a person as a specialist are given. In contrast to the previously developed views that the formation of a person as a specialist depends on age and length of service, the author has shown that the professional skills of a person are not a function of these parameters, but on the contrary, they are determined depending on the stage of the individual's professional formation. perceptions of specialists, as well as a description of the criteria of professional formation. The need for continuous development of the system of training qualified personnel and the fact that a person with many years of experience in various production fields does not fully realize his potential has created the problem of a person manifesting himself in all aspects of professional activity.

Without solving these problems, it is impossible to implement successful quality education and planning for future professional activities. The practical importance of this problem has shown the importance of studying it in psychology as well as in various disciplines.

Difficulties in learning the process of professional formation are the orientation of skills and professional abilities to normative activities based on a certain method of performing work. Therefore, the level of professional maturity is not distinguished, but only age and the time spent as a specialist are taken into account. The issue of professional formation of a person has been studied by many authors.

This is a common process in human development. Often, a complete analysis of the personality of the specialist is omitted, and the stage of the professional formation of the person is considered in accordance with the stage of the life path. Therefore, it is strictly limited in time. When studying the professional formation of a person working in social

spheres, it is important to pay attention to the different types of social relations between the subject and the social environment, which fully reveal the human capabilities.

It is important for us to divide each social relationship into subtypes such as interpersonal and sociability. In the first type, the subject is characterized by the fact that he has found himself, does not want to change himself and his activities. The second type is explained by the subject's search for himself. This is a transition, an intermediate state. An individual (or society) leaves one form and reaches another higher level of society. For harmonic relations, the subject appears as a whole person, which is determined by the condition of the subject-object order - role mask. Here man is in the state of absolute movement of development. Vocational education to students, taking into account the socio-economic needs of local conditions, the needs of one or another profession, specialists, the content of professional work in various professions, the demands of the profession on a person, the conditions of material and moral stimulation of working conditions, to inform the types of educational institutions where the profession can be acquired, that is, students will get acquainted with the character and peculiarities of various professions and specialties.

Vocational counseling has an individual character and helps some students to understand the characteristics of the profession they want to take up and their opportunities. Vocational diagnostics - it is assumed that the person of the subject of choosing a profession for students is compatible with the requirements of the chosen profession.

Vocational selection (selection) is a process of identifying individuals who can successfully occupy a certain profession and fulfill their civic (private) duty at a high level. Based on professional knowledge, certain skills, qualifications, based on examination criteria, rational selection is carried out. Professional orientation is considered a manifestation of the orientation of a person's personality, and this situation penetrates into his deep personality structures. Professional orientation is based on individual-psychological and individual-typological characteristics of a person, his value system, stereotypes, abilities and interests. It is formed at school, university, by what people around tell them and by their own independent studies. It will also be necessary to organize introductory classes for children related to the profession at school. In this, children will learn about many professions and the opportunities for choosing a profession will expand. It will be more clear which colleges and lyceums they will enter in the next stages along with their progress to higher grades.

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